

EFFECT OF THE DESIGN GUIDELINES ON THE DESIGN SPACE

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ABSTRACT

Lamination parameters are being increasingly used for lamination angles optimization of composite laminates. Moreover, the typical design guidelines affect the feasible region of the lamination parameters. This work aims at characterizing the boundaries and discrete nature of the feasible region of laminates when design guidelines are applied. The approach used was generating a set of laminate databases and filtering according the desired design guideline. This procedure is demonstrated to be very robust and effective.

1 INTRODUCTION

The optimization of the stacking sequence of composite structures is a quite difficult task. In aerospace applications, there are several loadings to be considered with constraints of buckling loads, natural frequencies, aeroelasticity and strength. The optimization of elastic performance of composite aeronautical structures is quite relevant as they are typically the most relevant design requirements. Moreover, these analyses are always computationally very demanding. This requires the optimization algorithms to be simultaneously efficient and robust. Efficiency is important because, even with the computational power of the modern computers, one can not afford to compute the objective function many times. The robustness is necessary to guarantee a good design despite the fact that only a very small fraction of the total design space is actually computed. These opposing requirements make the optimization of composite aeronautical structures very challenging.

Traditionally, the stiffness of a lamina is written in terms of products of trigonometric functions of the angle of each layer to some power. Therefore, if lamination angles are used as design variables, the problem is non-convex and the gradients could be very ill conditioned. Moreover, even with a modest amount of layers and the lamination angles constrained to be 0°, 90°, 45° or -45° there will be a very large number of combinations. Therefore, the use of lamination angles as design variables is certainly unfeasible in practical applications.

The lamination parameters were introduced by Tsai and Pagano [1] in 1968. They are defined in terms of sums of sine and cosine of multiples of the lamination angles of the laminate. They possess three important characteristics: (i) there are always eight parameters regardless the number layers of the laminate provided that the laminate is symmetric; (ii) they are defined to be non-dimensional quantities in the interval [-1,1]; and (iii) the laminate constitutive equations and, consequently, the finite element stiffness matrix are linear functions of the lamination parameters.

The academic community noticed the good potential of lamination parameters for optimization [2-4]. They are interesting as design variables since there are always only eight lamination parameters regardless the number of layers of a symmetric laminate where all lamina have equal material

properties. Moreover, the fact that the stiffness transformation is linear in terms of lamination parameters makes the optimization problems of elastic behavior convex and the gradient well behaved.

However, there is a major problem that hinders the use of the lamination parameters in optimization problems. It is very simple to compute the corresponding lamination parameters of the laminate for a given set of lamination angles. On the other hand, obtaining the lamination angles for a given set of lamination parameters requires the solution of a non-linear problem. Therefore, there could be a single solution, several solutions or no solution for this problem. The fact that there are sets of lamination parameters that do not correspond to any physical laminate imposes a difficult problem: if lamination parameters are used as design variables, they would have to be limited to a feasible region that it is very complex and changes with the number of layers [5-7]. In fact, for a small number of layers, the feasible region is not convex.

Another aspect that has to be accounted for is the fact that in practical applications there is a limited number of lamination angles that are used. The typically used fiber directions are 0° , 90° , 45° or -45° . This concept makes the design space for composite laminates discrete rather than continuous. That is, the laminations parameters are also discrete even though they are defined to be continuous.

The use of design guidelines imposes further constrains the design space. The use of symmetric laminates are almost always used to avoid thermal coupling by completely eliminating the coupling matrix $[B]$. Another frequently used design guideline is to minimize the mechanical couplings of matrices $[A]$ and $[D]$. The coupling terms of matrix $[A]$ can be easily eliminated by using balanced laminates. This makes lamination parameters ξ_2 and ξ_4 equal to zero. Unfortunately, eliminating the coupling terms of matrix $[D]$, that is, making ξ_6 and ξ_8 equal to zero is virtually impossible. The alternative is to minimize these terms by design.

Another important design guideline is to avoid repeating the same angle orientation for consecutive unidirectional layers to avoid fatigue problems. The minimum fiber orientation difference between consecutive layers is usually 45° . Also, a common practice in practical application is limiting the number of repeated layers to 4. This important design guideline affects the feasible region for the lamination parameters associated with matrix $[D]$. This effect is very difficult to be mathematically expressed.

Other popular design guidelines are the 10% rule [8] and the AML (% Angle plies Minus % Longitudinal plies) [9-10]. In reference [8] the authors proposed a mathematical description of the constraints imposed by the 10% rule on the lamination parameters.

Recently [11], a new procedure was proposed to solve this problem. The idea is to use a large number of laminates (around 80,000) to characterize the feasible region. This deals very naturally with the feasible region and with the discrete nature of the problem. It can also describe the changes in the feasible region due to virtually any design guideline. This is done by simply filtering out the laminates in the database that do not comply with the design guidelines. It is important to mention that the laminate databases need to be constructed only once.

Effectively, this approach works with actual laminates and takes advantage of all significant features of the lamination parameters for optimization. In reference [11], this procedure was demonstrated to be very efficient and robust.

In this paper, this approach will be used to characterize the design space of lamination parameters using the above design guidelines.

2 LAMINATION PARAMETERS

The constitutive law for a composite laminate is [1]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \{N\} \\ \{M\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\epsilon_m\} \\ \{\kappa\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $\{N\}$ and $\{M\}$ are stress resultants for force and moment, respectively. $\{\epsilon_m\}$ and $\{\kappa\}$ are the strains and curvatures at mid-plane, respectively. $[A]$, $[B]$ and $[D]$ are the laminate matrices for stiffness. Each of their six independent components (xx , yy , xy , xs , ys , ss) can be written as:

$$\{A\} = T[\Psi^A]\{U\} \quad (2)$$

$$\{B\} = \frac{T^2}{4}[\Psi^B]\{U\} \quad (3)$$

$$\{D\} = \frac{T^3}{12}[\Psi^D]\{U\} \quad (4)$$

where T is the total laminate thickness:

$$[\Psi^i] = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_E^i & 0 & \xi_\Delta^i & 0 & \xi_v^i & 0 \\ \xi_E^i & 0 & -\xi_\Delta^i & 0 & \xi_v^i & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_G^i & 0 & 0 & -\xi_v^i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\xi_{c_1}^i}{2} & 0 & -\xi_{c_2}^i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\xi_{c_1}^i}{2} & 0 & \xi_{c_2}^i \\ \xi_E^i & -2\xi_G^i & 0 & 0 & -\xi_v^i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\{U\}^T = \{U_E, U_G, U_{\Delta c}, U_{\Delta c}, U_{vc}, U_{vc}\} \quad (6)$$

where U_i are the material invariants.

For a laminate where all layers have the same material and thickness, the lamination parameters in equation (5) are:

$$\{\xi_\Delta^A, \xi_G^A, \xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3, \xi_4\} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \{\Phi\} \quad (7)$$

$$\{\xi_\Delta^B, \xi_G^B, \xi_9, \xi_{10}, \xi_{11}, \xi_{12}\} = \frac{2}{T} \sum_{k=1}^n (h_k + h_{k-1}) \{\Phi\} \quad (8)$$

$$\{\xi_\Delta^A, \xi_G^A, \xi_5, \xi_6, \xi_7, \xi_8\} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{4}{T^3} (h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3) \{\Phi\} \quad (9)$$

with

$$\{\Phi\} = \{1, 1, \cos 2\theta_k, \sin 2\theta_k, \cos 4\theta_k, \sin 4\theta_k\} \quad (10)$$

In equations (7) - (9), n is the total number of layer; h_k is the position of the upper part of the k^{th} layer with respect to the laminate midplane. θ_k is the fiber orientation of the k^{th} layers. The materials invariants are defined as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} U_E \\ U_G \\ U_{\Delta c} \\ U_{vc} \end{Bmatrix} = \lambda \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 & 2 & 4 \\ 1 & 1 & -2 & 4 \\ 4 & -4 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -2 & -4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} E_1 \\ E_2 \\ \nu_{12} E_2 \\ G_{12}/(8\lambda) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where $\lambda = 1/8(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$ and E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} , ν_{21} and G_{12} , are the engineering elastic constants of the material.

Notice that for balanced symmetric laminates matrix $[B]$ is zero, thus $\{\xi_{\Delta}^B, \xi_G^B, \xi_9, \xi_{10}, \xi_{11}, \xi_{12}\} = 0$. Also, for balanced laminates the coupling terms of matrix $[A]$ are zero, therefore, $\xi_2 = \xi_4 = 0$. From these definitions results that, for laminates with a single material, $\xi_{\Delta}^A = \xi_G^A = \xi_{\Delta}^D = \xi_G^D = 1$.

3 DESIGN SPACE ACCOUNTING FOR DESIGN GUIDELINES

Four sets of design guidelines were studied. The basic guidelines are: symmetric and balanced laminate with a maximum of four repeated consecutive unidirectional consecutive layers. The minimum angle variation between consecutive layers was assumed to be 45° . All sets of design guidelines were assumed to satisfy these basic requirements. A first set of design guidelines, named “Basic” is composed of all laminates within the laminate database that satisfy all the basic design guidelines.

A second one named “Homothetic” satisfies all the basic design guidelines and an additional one that shrinks homothetically the feasible region for matrix $[A]$, that is, lamination parameters ξ_1 and ξ_3 . Mathematically, this design guideline may be expressed as:

$$\beta \geq \xi_3 \geq \frac{2\xi_1^2}{\alpha} - \alpha \quad (12)$$

In this paper values of α and β were assumed to be equal to 0.8.

The third set of design guidelines assumes all the basic guidelines and the 10% rule. This implies that the fiber orientations are restricted to 0° , 90° , 45° or -45° and the minimum percentage of each type of these orientations has to be 10%. This set of guidelines is named “10% rule”.

Finally, the set of guidelines named “AML”, satisfies all basic guidelines, uses only 0° , 90° , 45° or -45° as fiber orientations and have to satisfy the AML criterion that is expressed as [10]:

$$\begin{aligned} AML &= \text{percentage}(+45^\circ) + \text{percentage}(-45^\circ) - \text{percentage}(0^\circ) \\ 70\% &\geq AML \geq -10\% \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Laminate databases of basic symmetric and balanced laminates with 16 layers were created accounting for a maximum of four repeated consecutive layers. One database used angles multiples of 15° and the other multiples of 45° . In first step only positive orientation angles were considered as lamination parameters $\xi_1, \xi_3, \xi_5, \xi_7$ are defined as cosines of the orientation angles and therefore do not depend on the sign. In a second step, all possible combination of the signs are considered to minimize the coupling terms, that is, the lamination parameters are $\xi_2, \xi_4, \xi_6, \xi_8$ minimized. Then the laminate databases were filtered using the design guidelines to characterize the correspondent feasible region.

These laminate databases characterize the design space in terms of lamination parameters in terms of number of layers (either 12 or 16), the angle increment for fiber angle orientation (15° or 45°) with application of the design rules. This procedure is very robust, straightforward and has to be done only once. Laminate databases have been successfully used for optimization purposes combined with a metamodel and a simply optimization procedure. This optimization procedure proved to be robust and very efficient.

Table 1 lists the number of laminates within the each laminate database. Also, figures 1-4 depict the design space in terms of lamination parameters for matrix $[A]$ (ξ_1, ξ_3) and matrix $[D]$ (ξ_5, ξ_7) It is clear that using $\Delta\theta = 15^\circ$ produces a much denser set of databases than 45° . It is also evident that the database for matrix $[A]$ is quite sparse even for 16 layers. Moreover, using the 10%, homothetic or AML rules further constrain the design space particularly for matrix $[A]$. Matrix $[D]$ design space is not much affected by these design guidelines.

Matrix $[A]$ determines the in-plane mechanical behaviour of the laminate and matrix $[D]$ determines its bending/torsion behaviour. Considering, for example, a typical box beam with thin skins, matrix $[A]$ is important to define global buckling and the beam vibration modes. Matrix $[D]$ is relevant for local buckling and vibration modes. Moreover, in this case, matrix $[A]$ is very relevant for strain and stresses at the skins. Therefore, both matrices typically need to be taken into account in terms of design.

	$\Delta\theta = 15^\circ$		$\Delta\theta = 45^\circ$	
	12 layers	16 layers	12 layers	16 layers
Basic	5525	212343	335	2985
Homothetic	4602	201210	288	2790
10% rule	-	-	231	2544
AML	-	-	219	1715

Table 1: Number of laminates in the database.

Figure 1: Design space for matrix $[A]$ (ξ_1, ξ_3) for 12 and 16 layers and $\Delta\theta = 15^\circ$.

(a) Basic 12 layers

(b) Basic 16 layers

(c) Homothetic 12 layers

(d) Homothetic 16 layers

Figure 2: Design space for matrix $[D]$ (ξ_5, ξ_7) for 12 and 16 layers and $\Delta\theta = 15^\circ$.

Figure 3: Design space for matrix $[A]$ (ξ_1, ξ_3) for 12 and 16 layers and $\Delta\theta = 45^\circ$.

Figure 4: Design space for matrix $[D]$ (ξ_5 , ξ_7) for 12 and 16 layers and $\Delta\theta = 45^\circ$.

4 OPTIMIZATION EXAMPLE

In order to further clarify the impact of the design guidelines in optimizing laminates, a simple example will be presented. A minimum value for the longitudinal modulus of elasticity (E_{ref}) and in-plane shear modulus (G_{ref}) are defined. Two sub-objective functions are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= \frac{E_{xx}}{E_{ref}} \\ F_2 &= \frac{G_{xy}}{G_{ref}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Since all laminates in the databases are balanced, the longitudinal modulus of elasticity, E_{xx} , and the in-plane shear modulus, G_{xy} , can be computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{xx} &= A_{xx} - \frac{A_{xy}^2}{A_{yy}} \\ G_{xy} &= \frac{1}{A_{ss}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

It is easy to relate matrix [A] components with the lamination parameters using equation (2).

A min-max approach is adopted: the objective function to be maximized is the minimum between sub-objective functions F_1 and F_2 . The material properties used are listed in Table 2.

Engineering constant		Value
E_1	[GPa]	132.0
E_2	[GPa]	10.8
ν_{12}	–	0.24
G_{12}	[GPa]	5.6

Table 2: Material properties.

The optimization procedure maximizes the minimum between F_1 and F_2 . This means that if, for example, E_{ref} is set with a low value, the tendency is that F_1 will have a large value and the shear modulus G_{xy} will be maximized. On the other hand, if G_{ref} is chosen to be a small value, E_{xx} will tend to be maximized. Therefore, E_{ref} and G_{ref} define the relative importance of maximizing E_{xx} or G_{xy} . Three cases described in Table 3 were considered. One with small E_{ref} , one with small G_{ref} , and the third one being a mid-term.

Table 4-6 lists the results obtained for databases for cases a, b and c, respectively.

Optimization cases	E_{ref} GPa	G_{ref} GPa
Case a	50	15
Case b	10	15
Case c	50	3

Table 3: Optimization cases.

Design guideline	Number of layers	$\Delta\theta$ (°)	E_{xx} (MPa)	G_{xy} (MPa)	ξ_1	ξ_3	F_{obj}
Basic	12	15	79147	24266	0.62	-0.15	1.58
	16	15	80811	23672	0.55	-0.11	1.58
	12	45	64146	26937	0.33	-0.33	1.28
	16	45	83947	22040	0.50	0.00	1.47
Homothetic	12	15	77641	24266	0.50	-0.15	1.55
	16	15	78006	23672	0.46	-0.11	1.56
	12	45	64146	26937	0.33	-0.33	1.28
	16	45	83947	22040	0.50	0.00	1.47
10% rule	12	45	84834	17143	0.33	0.33	1.14
	16	45	71379	22040	0.25	0.00	1.43
AML	12	45	64146	26937	0.33	-0.33	1.28
	16	45	71379	22040	0.25	0.00	1.43

Table 4: Optimization results for case a.

Design guideline	Number of layers	$\Delta\theta$ (°)	E_{xx} (MPa)	G_{xy} (MPa)	ξ_1	ξ_3	F_{obj}
Basic	12	15	24376	36880	0.00	-1.00	2.44
	16	15	24376	36880	0.00	-1.00	2.44
	12	45	24376	36880	0.00	-1.00	2.44
	16	45	24376	36880	0.00	-1.00	2.44
Homothetic	12	15	37430	31834	0.00	-0.66	2.12
	16	15	34228	33170	0.00	-0.75	2.21
	12	45	28518	26937	-0.33	-0.33	1.80
	16	45	54214	29460	0.25	-0.50	1.96
10% rule	12	45	47882	26937	0.00	-0.33	1.80
	16	45	42733	29460	0.00	-0.50	1.96
AML	12	45	28518	26937	-0.33	-0.33	1.80
	16	45	42733	29460	0.00	-0.50	1.96

Table 5: Optimization results for case b.

Design guideline	Number of layers	$\Delta\theta$ (°)	E_{xx} (MPa)	G_{xy} (MPa)	ξ_1	ξ_3	F_{obj}
Basic	12	15	120009	7200	0.66	1.00	2.40
	16	15	116727	14620	0.83	0.50	2.33
	12	45	120009	7200	0.66	1.00	2.40
	16	45	113430	14620	0.75	0.50	2.27
Homothetic	12	15	106796	12246	0.56	0.66	2.14
	16	15	109578	12839	0.62	0.62	2.19
	12	45	103225	17143	0.66	0.33	2.06
	16	45	99339	14620	0.50	0.50	1.99
10% rule	12	45	84834	17143	0.33	0.33	1.70
	16	45	99339	14620	0.50	0.50	1.99
AML	12	45	64176	17143	0.00	0.33	1.28
	16	45	99339	14620	0.50	0.50	1.99

Table 6: Optimization results for case c.

The results depending on the number of layers there is a tendency to have a larger effect of the design guidelines. For example, taking case c (that tends to optimize the modulus of elasticity), using 12 layers and $\Delta\theta = 45^\circ$, there is a large difference between the optima among the design criteria. The modulus of elasticity for the AML guideline is 64,2 GPa, for the 10% rule is 84,8 GPa for the homothetic is 106,8 GPa and finally, for the basic guidelines is 120,0 GPa. So, for this particular example, there is indeed a large difference. For 16 layers, the difference is still relevant but much smaller.

For case b, the differences are quite small because the global optimum is closely represented for all guidelines. For case c, again the differences are very significant.

5 CONCLUSIONS

An important conclusion of this work is that the use of laminate databases is very simple to implement and it is efficient and robust. Any optimization could be performed using this technique but a simpler problem is more effective in terms of demonstrating the impact of the choice of the design guidelines on the quality of the design.

It is clear that the design space is neither convex nor continuous. The plots for matrix [A] are quite impressive because they are very sparse. For example, the 10% rule has only four laminates for 12 layers and nine for 16 layers among 213 or 2544. An important point to notice is the fact that matrix [A] does not depend upon the stacking sequence. Any permutation of the layers will be result in the very same values for ξ_1 e ξ_3 . Therefore, many different laminates correspond to a single point in the plane ξ_1 e ξ_3 . This implies that the plane for matrix [A] is quite sparse and there is a significant difference among the various design guidelines.

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